

Strategies for students' well-being development: the task-oriented classroom approach

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Article Info

Article history:

Received Apr 4, 2024

Revised Aug 15, 2024

Accepted Sep 2, 2024

Keywords:

Academic achievement

Learning environment

School climate

Student well-being

Task orientation

ABSTRACT

Promoting students' well-being is a vital aspect of education. Creating a conducive classroom learning environment is essential, and task orientation plays a significant role. This paper aims to explore three research objectives related to the influence of the learning environment on student well-being by focusing on creating a task-oriented learning environment. The study employs a quantitative approach with a cross-sectional study design. The study analyzed 1,698 students (676 male and 994 female students) from nine cities in East Java, Indonesia. The results of the simultaneous regression analysis showed that $R=.578$, $R^2=.334$, and $p<.10$. The learning environment was found to predict student well-being by 33.4% significantly. At the same time, task orientation was identified as the most dominant factor affecting student well-being. The study's findings suggest that task orientation could be a solution to enhance student well-being in classroom learning practices. This study suggests the need for teacher development to improve teachers' professional ability to facilitate learning in the classroom. Future research should consider using central variables, including moderating and intervening variables, to explore the relationship between the learning environment and student well-being.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Many schools' efforts to develop student well-being at every level of education in Indonesia have failed. The first failure is indicated by many school activities that cause students to experience insecurity and psychological distress [1], [2]. Second, many teachers have difficulty determining and carrying out learning that aligns with the student's demands and needs [3], [4]. Third, the cooperation between schools and parents continues to face challenges in preserving students' well-being [5], [6]. This condition suggests the importance of the school's role in developing students' well-being in and outside the classroom.

Research on fostering well-being within educational settings has identified three primary approaches. Initially, well-being is nurtured through classroom-based educational activities [7], [8]. Next, it enhances well-being by establishing supportive conditions beyond the classroom [9], [10]. Lastly, schools engage with parents to promote students' well-being at home [11], [12]. This paper delves deeper into enhancing classroom well-being by designing tasks that create a focused learning atmosphere. The uniqueness of this study lies in its examination of task-oriented aspects in the development of student well-being.

Student well-being is a multidimensional construct used to describe the well-being condition of students in a school context. Student well-being refers to how schools can optimally accommodate student needs and expectations [13], [14]. Student well-being in school should represent the dimensions of positive attitudes and emotions toward school, being comfortable and happy in school, having a positive academic self-concept and self-esteem, having no worries, somatic complaints, and physical and social problems [13], [15]. Therefore, to support student well-being in educational settings, schools should at least meet students' needs to function cognitively, affectively, socially, physically, and economically so they can achieve happiness.

Task orientation within the classroom learning environment is key to fostering student well-being. Task orientation is defined as the drive to accomplish academic tasks [16], [17]. Various studies have linked task orientation to positive outcomes in students' feelings of autonomy, competency, and satisfaction [18], [19]. These studies suggest that when students perceive a task-oriented climate, it correlates with fulfilling their autonomy, competence, and satisfaction needs. Therefore, it is evident that establishing a task-oriented atmosphere in the classroom can help students cultivate a sense of well-being characterized by feelings of independence, skillfulness, and fulfillment.

This article aims to describe three research objectives relating to the influence of the learning environment on well-being. The first goal is to describe the well-being of students at three levels of education. The purpose of the description is to classify well-being. The second goal is to test the influence of the learning environment on student well-being. Testing is conducted simultaneously and partially. Simultaneous testing aims to test the overall effect of environment learning on well-being, while partial testing aims to test each learning environment on well-being. The third goal is to test the task orientation, which is the most important to well-being. The analysis continued by testing the interrelationship between task orientation and well-being aspects. The three goals of this project are to provide alternative learning activities to enhance students' well-being in the classroom.

This article posits that student well-being is not a fixed attribute, but quality teachers can nurture and enhance it through various strategies implemented inside and outside the classroom. To explore the concept, the current study presents two central hypotheses. The first hypothesis suggests that the learning environment, encompassing everything from the physical space to the emotional and psychological atmosphere, is crucial in fostering student well-being within schools. The second hypothesis delves into the specific strategy of task orientation, proposing that this focused approach to learning and goal achievement within the classroom can significantly enhance student well-being. Confirming these hypotheses may highlight the potential of targeted educational strategies in promoting well-being and introduce a novel perspective of student well-being by empirically linking task orientation, a traditionally academic-focused strategy, directly to the emotional and psychological domain of student well-being. Thus, it can broaden the scope of interventions available to educators aiming to cultivate a supportive and thriving school environment.

2. METHOD

The method section of this study provides a meticulous explanation of four pivotal elements: research design, research subjects, data collection, and data analysis. The research design outlines the systematic approach adopted, specifying whether the study is qualitative, quantitative, or mixed-methods, and details the structure of the investigation. The section on research subjects describes the demographic and characteristic criteria for participant selection, ensuring the sample accurately represents the population under study. The data collection section elucidates the methods employed to gather relevant information. Lastly, the data analysis section discusses the statistics used to interpret the collected data, highlighting the strategies for uncovering patterns, trends, and insights within the research findings. Each of these components plays a crucial role in the overall integrity and validity of the study, providing a clear and comprehensive framework for understanding the research method.

2.1. Research design

This study employs a quantitative method, utilizing a cross-sectional design to gather and analyze numerical data through statistical methods. The core objective is to rigorously test hypotheses regarding the diverse learning environments and their impacts on students' well-being. The research incorporates simultaneous and partial testing apps to understand comprehensively. Simultaneous testing was employed to examine the collective influence of various learning environments on student well-being, offering insights into how these factors influence the overall educational experience. In addition, the researchers also used partial testing to precisely pinpoint the particular learning environment that exerts the most dominant influence on student well-being. These dual testing strategies provide a broad overview of the learning environments' effects and highlight key areas that significantly enhance or diminish student well-being, allowing for targeted interventions and improvements in educational practices.

2.2. Research procedure

The questionnaire distribution was carefully planned to accommodate the large sample size and ensure reliable data collection. The paper-based questionnaires were administered during scheduled class times for around two years. Trained research assistants and students instructed as data collectors visited each participating school and distributed the questionnaires to the students in a controlled classroom environment, ensuring minimal disruptions and maintaining consistency in data collection procedures. These student data collectors were equipped with knowledge on how to gather data properly. Pilot testing was conducted with a small group of students to identify and rectify issues related to understanding and interpretation. Moreover, informed consent was obtained from students and their parents or guardians, and measures were implemented to ensure the anonymity and confidentiality of respondents by using unique identifiers instead of names.

2.3. Research subject

This study involves 1,698 students (705 males and 993 females) from nine cities in East Java Province, Indonesia, divided into three education levels: i) elementary school students aged 11 to 13 (n=300; 139 males and 161 females); ii) junior high school students aged 13 to 15 (n=758; 406 males and 352 female); and iii) senior high school students aged 16 to 18 (n=640; 160 males and 480 females). Subjects were selected based on school recommendations and were provided with consent letters. The researchers employed a random sampling to minimize bias and ensure that the sample is representative of the entire population. Thus, each member of the population has an equal chance of being selected for inclusion in the study. The random sampling involved selecting students from each education level and city without any predetermined criteria, such as academic performance or socioeconomic status. By randomly selecting participants, the researchers aim to mitigate the risk of introducing systematic errors into the findings, thereby increasing the validity and reliability of the results.

Random sampling was employed to ensure every student had an equal chance of being selected, reducing selection bias. Follow-up visits were made to ensure a high response rate, with questionnaires reviewed for completeness and any inconsistencies clarified with respondents. Trained student data collectors assisted in this process, and data quality checks were performed to address potential biases. These strategies, including pilot testing, random sampling, ongoing follow-up, and involving trained student data collectors, ensured reliable data collection and supported the study's validity. The sample size was determined using statistical power analysis and practical considerations, resulting in 1,698 students (705 males and 993 females) from nine cities in East Java Province, Indonesia. The statistical power analysis sets the minimum sample size required for detecting a statistically significant effect, considering an alpha level of .05, a power of .80, and an expected moderate effect size from similar educational psychology studies [20], [21]. This approach ensures the sample size is sufficient to generalize findings and understand the learning environment's impact on student well-being.

2.4. Data collections

The data collection involves two research measuring instruments on a Likert scale (1 to 5 score). The first instrument is what is happening in this class (WIHIC)? It is used to measure the seven learning environments. This scale was developed by Fraser at Curtin University, Australia. The WIHIC questionnaire is one of these tools used globally to measure students' perceptions of their classroom environment across various dimensions, including student cohesion, teacher support, investigation, task orientation, collaboration, and equity. Each type of learning environment consists of eight statement items. So, the number of items in this measuring instrument amounts to 5. Researchers have tested this measuring instrument in Indonesia. The test results showed that the reliability level of this measuring instrument reached Cronbach's alpha coefficient of .86 to .96 [22]. The second measurement is the Warwick-Edinburgh mental well-being scale (WEMWBS), developed at the Universities of Warwick and Edinburgh. It was specifically created by Stewart-Brown at Warwick Medical School, along with colleagues from the University of Edinburgh. The scale was used to measure five indicators of student well-being: satisfaction, competence, relatedness, and autonomy. The items on this instrument amount are up to 14 statements. This measuring instrument's validity has been tested in various countries, including Asia. Test results in Iranian study context show Cronbach's alpha values of .84 to .93 [23], and in Indonesia as well as China has Cronbach's alpha values of .90 [24]. Both measuring instruments used in the study show a high-reliability score.

2.5. Data analysis

In this study, data analysis encompasses descriptive and inferential techniques to delve into the impact of learning environments on student well-being. Descriptive statistics, through means and standard deviations, lay the initial groundwork by summarizing the central tendencies and variabilities. Building on this, inferential analysis via regression allows for a deeper exploration of causal relationships, particularly how

different facets of the learning environment contribute to student well-being. The study assesses the collective influence of various classroom strategies, with a partial focus on the role of task orientation across different educational levels. It offers a nuanced understanding of the factors that enhance or impede student well-being.

3. RESULTS

The results section reveals three essential insights into the promotion of student well-being in class. It discusses general well-being levels among students, evaluates the influence of the learning environment on these levels, and investigates the crucial role of task orientation in improving student well-being. These findings underscore the importance of a supportive and task-oriented classroom environment for fostering better student well-being.

3.1. Demographic of the research subject

This section provides a description of the research subjects, including gender distribution, school status, the educational level they belong to, and their age range. All these demographic details are crucial for the study's context and are systematically presented in Table 1 for a thorough understanding and analysis. Table 1 provides an overview of the research subjects, highlighting variations in task orientation and well-being based on gender, school status, and age group. Female students exhibit slightly higher task orientation than males, but male students report marginally better well-being. Differences between public and private school students are minimal, suggesting school status has little impact on these variables. Younger students (elementary level) show significantly higher task orientation but lower well-being than older students. The junior and senior high school students have consistent task orientation levels, but their well-being varies more, decreasing at ages 14-15 and slightly improving at 16 and older. This condition suggests that age and educational stage have a more complex effect on students' well-being than on their task orientation.

Table 1. Profile of the research subject (N=1,698)

No	Research subject	N	%	Task orientation		Well-being	
				Mean	SD	Mean	SD
1	Gender						
	Male	705	41.52	32.66	5.52	56.51	8.91
	Female	993	58.48	33.53	5.65	55.84	7.97
2	School status						
	State school	1,045	61.54	32.85	4.94	56.20	7.86
	Private school	653	38.46	32.63	5.13	56.17	8.65
3	Elementary school	300	17.67	59.70	7.29	34.85	4.46
	11 years old	168	9.89	59.35	7.89	34.85	5.14
	12 years old	110	6.48	60.47	6.31	35.06	3.91
	13 years old	22	1.30	58.59	7.08	33.77	3.50
4	Junior high school	758	44.64	32.54	5.70	54.90	8.83
	13 years old	324	19.08	32.76	5.95	54.86	9.78
	14 years old	370	21.79	32.18	5.49	55.05	8.22
	15 years old	64	3.77	33.48	5.55	54.25	6.98
5	Senior high school	640	37.69	33.14	5.88	55.89	7.84
	16 years old	202	11.90	34.30	5.55	56.58	7.35
	17 years old	329	19.38	32.26	6.08	55.07	8.41
	18 years old	109	6.42	33.66	5.49	57.06	6.61

Table 2 presents a detailed analysis of student well-being across different educational stages, revealing a trend of gradually decreasing mean scores from elementary to senior high school, with elementary students exhibiting the highest levels of well-being and associated factors such as satisfaction, affection, competence, relatedness, and autonomy. The skewness and kurtosis values indicate a variety of distribution shapes, with a notable peak in affection at the elementary level and an exceptional peak in competence among senior high students, suggesting a tighter clustering of responses around the mean for these variables. These statistical indicators suggest nuanced shifts in student well-being perceptions and experiences as they progress through their educational journey, highlighting the complexity of factors contributing to student well-being across different school levels (Table 2).

3.2. The effect of the learning environment on students' well-being

The results of simultaneous regression analysis of the influence of the learning environment (task orientation, cohesiveness, cooperation, involvement, equity, investigation, and support) on students' well-being at three educational levels showed values of $R=.578$. $R^2=.334$ $p<.10$. The learning environment

significantly predicts high and low well-being in students of 33.4%. Furthermore, the regression analysis findings for elementary school data indicated an R-value of .624, an R^2 value of .389, and a p value of <.10. For junior high school data, the analysis showed a R value of .527, an R^2 value of .278, and a p value of <.10. Lastly, the senior high school data revealed a R value of .598, an R^2 value of .357, and a p value of <.10.

The results showed that the learning environment affected elementary school students' well-being by 38.9%, high school students by 35.78%, and junior high school students by 27.8%. Furthermore, the results of a partial regression analysis that tested the type of learning environment of student well-being at three levels of education are presented in Table 3. The analysis in Table 3 demonstrates that task orientation is a dominant variable positively influencing student outcomes across all educational levels, from elementary to senior high school. Its consistently high beta values and significant p-values underscore its pivotal role in shaping student success, regardless of age or educational stage. It suggests that a focus on task-oriented activities and goals is a crucial driver of academic achievement, highlighting the fundamental importance of task orientation in the educational process at every level.

Table 2. Description of student well-being

Variable	Mean	Standard deviation	Normality test		
			Skewness	Kurtosis	
Elementary school (N=300)	Well-being	59.70	7.29	-1.50	4.52
	Satisfaction	12.75	2.04	-1.03	1.32
	Affection	17.51	2.25	-1.76	6.60
	Competence	8.16	1.62	-.981	1.11
	Relatedness	12.71	2.14	-.916	.558
	Autonomy	8.56	1.49	-1.47	2.92
Junior high school (N=640)	Well-being	55.98	7.52	-.297	-.498
	Satisfaction	12.46	1.88	-.510	.002
	Affection	15.94	2.33	-.327	-.057
	Competence	7.67	1.47	-.087	-.537
	Relatedness	12.03	2.12	-.377	-.331
	Autonomy	7.86	1.54	-.554	.675
Senior high school (N=758)	Well-being	55.13	7.96	-.326	-.044
	Satisfaction	12.19	2.05	-.614	.124
	Affection	15.65	2.53	-.481	.150
	Competence	7.73	1.93	4.32	68.27
	Relatedness	11.75	2.31	-.536	.037
	Autonomy	7.79	1.59	-.614	.09

Table 3. The result of the partial analysis

No	Level of education	Variables	β	P
1	Elementary school	Task orientation (1)	.208	.001**
		Student cohesiveness (2)	.171	.003**
		Cooperation (3)	.128	.018*
		Involvement (4)	.158	.031*
		Equity (5)	.140	.039*
		Investigation (6)	.080	.240 ^{ns}
		Teacher support (7)	-.083	.137 ^{ns}
2	Junior high school	Task orientation (1)	.221	.000**
		Student cohesiveness (2)	.155	.000**
		Equity (3)	.113	.011*
		Cooperation (4)	.090	.020*
		Teacher support (5)	.080	.049*
		Involvement (6)	.032	.464 ^{ns}
		Investigation (7)	-.032	.398 ^{ns}
3	Senior high school	Task orientation (1)	.218	.000**
		Equity (2)	.158	.000**
		Involvement (3)	.117	.013**
		Student cohesiveness (4)	.111	.007*
		Cooperation (5)	.087	.025*
		Teacher support (6)	.065	.112 ^{ns}
		Investigation (7)	.048	.251 ^{ns}

Level of significance *=.005. **=.001; ns=no significant

3.3. Task orientation as a strategy for student's well-being development

The study meticulously examined the impact of task orientation on student well-being, employing a regression analysis to understand its influence. The analysis revealed that task orientation significantly predicts student well-being, accounting for 24.4% of the variance observed in this domain. More specifically,

the statistical outputs indicated an R-value of .494, which signifies the strength of the relationship between task orientation and student well-being. The R^2 value, standing at .244, quantifies that task orientation alone can explain a substantial portion of the variance in student well-being. This relationship's statistical significance was further validated by an F value of 548.638, coupled with a p-value below .10, confirming the pivotal role of task orientation. These numbers reflect the data-driven insights derived from our research, showcasing the quantifiable impact of task orientation on student well-being within educational settings.

Table 4 displays the intricate relationship between task orientation and various aspects of well-being, highlighting the significant interconnections among these crucial dimensions. Task orientation emerges as a pivotal factor, with its strong correlations to satisfaction, affection, competence, relatedness, and autonomy, underscoring its broad impact on individual well-being. The table presents a detailed analysis, with correlation coefficients indicating the strength and significance of these relationships, thereby offering insights into how a focus on task-oriented behaviors can influence a wide range of well-being outcomes.

Table 4. Interrelatedness between task orientation and well-being aspects

No.	Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6
1	Task-orientation	-	.406**	.398**	.393**	.332**	.413**
2	Satisfaction		-	.645**	.436**	.531**	.551**
3	Affection			-	.467**	.568**	.557**
4	Competence				-	.335**	.458**
5	Relatedness					-	.456**
6	Autonomy						-

Level of significance *=.005. **=.001

4. DISCUSSION

The study conclusively demonstrated that the learning environment critically impacts students' well-being, with task orientation in the classroom emerging as a particularly influential factor. The task orientation pertains to the extent of time and focus a teacher should allocate to teaching tasks, which fundamentally shapes the learning experience. The more time teachers dedicate to teaching a specific topic, the higher the chance that students will engage deeply and understand the material thoroughly. Teachers face the challenge of balancing the time spent on direct instruction, facilitating student questions, encouraging independent thought, and assessing student performance. These elements are vital for creating a dynamic and interactive learning atmosphere [25], [26]. Effective task orientation fosters a sense of purpose and direction in the classroom, enabling students to navigate their learning journey confidently. In summary, the teachers' role in effectively managing task orientation is crucial, directly influencing students' academic achievements and overall well-being.

The research elucidates that pedagogical proficiency in task management profoundly influences student well-being within the educational milieu. It posits that a teacher's adeptness in curriculum-aligned task formulation and execution and dynamic student engagement strategies engenders an optimal learning environment [27], [28]. This pedagogical approach catalyzes a heightened sense of student agency and engagement, fostering a conducive academic and emotional flourishing atmosphere. The intentional alignment of educational tasks with curricular objectives facilitates a meaningful immersion of students in the learning content, thereby enhancing their intrinsic motivation and psychological well-being [18], [29]. Consequently, the scholarly findings underscore the indispensable role of task-oriented teaching methodologies in advancing educational outcomes and significantly bolstering student well-being, thereby affirming its centrality in the constitution of a productive educational framework.

Reflecting on the outcomes of this research within the ongoing educational context emphasizes the profound influence of task orientation on student well-being. This reflective analysis underscores the necessity of fostering an inclusive and engaging learning environment where students are encouraged to participate actively and collaboratively in their educational journey. The study highlights the importance of integrating task orientation strategies that cater to diverse learning styles and needs, thus promoting a more personalized and effective learning experience [30]. By adopting such approaches, educators can significantly enhance students' academic performance and, more importantly, their well-being and satisfaction with the learning process [31]. The reflection concludes that task orientation is not merely a teaching strategy but a fundamental element shaping the educational landscape, influencing students' engagement, learning outcomes, and overall well-being. As such, educators and policymakers must recognize and leverage task orientation's potential to create more responsive and supportive educational environments.

Compared to previous research, this study introduces a novel perspective by focusing on the impact of task orientation on students' well-being, diverging from the traditional emphasis on academic success. This unique focus brings to light the multifaceted role of task orientation, not only in facilitating knowledge acquisition but also in enhancing the holistic well-being of students. Previous studies have predominantly concentrated on the cognitive and performance aspects of learning, often overlooking the emotional and psychological dimensions that are equally crucial for a comprehensive educational experience [32], [33]. By highlighting the significance of task orientation in promoting student well-being, this research contributes a valuable dimension to the existing body of knowledge, suggesting that task orientation can be a powerful tool in creating more balanced and nurturing learning environments. This study's focus on well-being as a pivotal outcome of effective task orientation marks a significant shift towards a more holistic understanding of education, where student well-being is prioritized alongside academic excellence.

This research contributes significantly to educational psychology by highlighting the role of task orientation in the learning environment and its positive effects on student well-being. By delving into the dynamics of how task orientation influences the classroom atmosphere and student engagement, the study offers fresh insights into the design and implementation of learning strategies that support not only academic achievement but also the overall well-being of students. This holistic approach to education, which considers learners' emotional, psychological, and cognitive development, is crucial for fostering an inclusive and supportive educational climate [34], [35]. The findings suggest that effective task orientation, characterized by well-structured tasks, clear objectives, and supportive teacher-student interactions, can be crucial in enhancing the quality of education and student life. Therefore, this research extends the boundaries of educational psychology by providing evidence of the integral role of task orientation in developing environments that nurture students' intellectual and emotional growth.

The implications of this research for educational practice are extensive and varied across different academic levels, including elementary, secondary, and tertiary education levels. At the primary level, task orientation can lay a solid foundation for developing essential learning skills and fostering a love for learning among young students. By introducing well-structured tasks that stimulate students' curiosity and engagement, educators can encourage the students to explore new concepts and ideas actively. At the secondary level (junior and senior high school), task orientation becomes increasingly critical as students face more complex subjects and academic challenges. Here, the focus shifts towards enhancing critical thinking and problem-solving skills, as well as deepening the understanding of subject matters through targeted tasks and activities. In tertiary education, task orientation is more sophisticated, supporting independent research, critical analysis, and innovation. By embedding task orientation within the curriculum, higher education institutions can prepare students for the complexities of the professional world and lifelong learning. Across all levels, task orientation's strategic application in educational settings is expected to enrich students' learning experience, promote student engagement, and foster a supportive and inclusive environment conducive to academic success and personal well-being.

5. CONCLUSION

The study results showed that task orientation could act as a solution to develop student well-being in classroom learning practices, as shown in a positive interaction between teachers and students, as well as an intensive and effective learning process. On the one hand, the teachers gave their time and focus on designing learning activities (planning, implementation, and assessment). On the other hand, students must be optimally involved in completing the assigned tasks to understand the material better. Thus, task orientation as a learning strategy provides opportunities for teachers and students to interact healthily.

Research that examines the learning environment in supporting student well-being has been intensively done. Some of these studies focused on various learning environments that affect multiple aspects of student life academically and non-academically. Moreover, the object of these studies focused on one educational level. Unlike previous research, the current study has investigated student well-being from primary to tertiary education and found that teacher task orientation in the classroom as a learning environment was influential in developing student well-being at these three educational levels. Thus, the current research can contribute to scientific development, especially in educational psychology.

The discovery of a direct link between teachers' task-focused approaches and student well-being prompts further investigation to deepen our understanding of this relationship. A critical question arises: is the observed correlation inherent, or do other factors act as intervening or moderating influences? This query highlights a significant limitation of the current study. To address this gap, the researchers recommend future research to include critical variables serving as interveners or moderators to elucidate the dynamics between teachers' task orientation and student well-being more clearly. Furthermore, the study advocates for adopting experimental methodologies to establish a causal connection between these variables more conclusively.

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